

Obituary

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The British healthcare system's loss of seventeen of its Muslim healthcare professionals (fourteen doctors and three nurses as of the 28th April) speaks for itself about the tremendous sacrifice that this community has made during this pandemic. The impact of their passing on their families and local communities has been devastating and we mourn their loss. The British Islamic Medical Association (BIMA) pay tribute to the sacrifice & heroism of these amazing health care professional who lost their lives in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic in the UK.

Dr Habib Zaidi originally from Pakistan is a GP who worked for around 50 years in Essex. He was well loved by his local community and was known as a fixture in the area. He had been a GP longer than many others had even been alive. He passed away after displaying textbook symptoms of COVID-19 and his death as one of the first in the medical community, sent shockwaves amongst his colleagues and fellow healthcare practitioners. His family and local community mourn his death. He passed away on 25.3.2020.

Dr Adil Al-Tayar was an Organ Transplant Surgeon of Sudanese origin. He was volunteering at the emergency department of Hereford Hospital at West of England when he starts feeling ill & self-isolate before getting worse to require admission & later on ventilation. In the space of 12 days, he went from working at the emergency department to passing away. His death was mourned by his family and local community and he will be remembered for his generosity and humour. He passed away on 25.3.2020.

Dr Amged El-Hawrani was an eminent front-line ENT surgeon at Queen's Hospital, Burton in Derbyshire originally from Sudan. He was instrumental in helping the Sudanese doctors in different stages of training in the UK & Sudan. He was known for being extremely hard-working and dedicated to his patients and even took part in a trek to the Himalayas to raise money for his local NHS Trust. His family and local community mourn his death. He passed away on 28.3.2020.

Dr Alfa Sa'adu was a Geriatrician of Nigerian Origin who started his career in London at 1976. He was previously medical director of Princess Alexandra Hospital in Harlow and medical director and consultant physician at Ealing Hospital before retiring. He came out of retirement to help assist in the fight against the pandemic which sadly resulted in his death. His various management positions speak volume about his leadership team working traits and he will be sorely missed by those in both the UK and Nigeria who knew him. He passed away on 28.3.2020.

Professor Sami Shousha was a Consultant Histopathologist at Charing Cross Hospital managing the breast Histopathology service. He was honorary professor at Imperial College London and worked at UK Cancer Research laboratories at Hammersmith Hospital since 1978. His longevity in working for the NHS is astounding and his family spoke of how much they would miss him. Previous tutees and students spoke of the way in which Professor Shousha's supervision touched their lives and helped them progress in their research areas. He will be sorely missed. He passed away on 2.4.2020.

Areema Nasreen was an enthusiastic young nurse at Walsall Manor Hospital; mother of three who started her career as a housekeeper the year she got married. She then studied to be nurse and graduated only last January. Unfortunately, her time in practice was short and she succumbed to COVID-19 leaving her family shocked and raw with grief. Her age at 36 meant that her family and friends were particularly surprised which deepened their anguish but spoke of how well loved and respected she was by her patients and colleagues. She will be missed. She passed away on 2.4.2020.

Dr Syed Zishan Haider was a British Pakistani GP who was working at the Valence Medical Centre in Dagenham before he passed away from COVID-19. He was known as a selfless man, driven by the need to help others. Even as he was struggling in his final hours from the disease he was urging doctors and nurses to pay attention to other patients and not him, underlying his selflessness. His death was a tragedy and we will be sorely missed by his family

and local community. He was 79 when he passed away on 6.4.2020.

Dr Fayez Ayache was born in Syria but had been living in the UK since the 1970s. He retired a couple of years ago but was back to working a few days a week as a GP with North Clacton Medical Group. He was well known for assisting Syria refugees in the local area over the last few years. His work as a rural GP touched the lives of the local community and his death shook the area. His family and local community mourn his passing as a heroic figure moves on. He passed away on 8.4.2020.

Dr Abdul Mabud Chowdhury was born in Bangladesh but and was urologist based in east London. He is well known for demanding the UK government to supply better PPE for medical workers in hospitals two weeks before his admission as a COVID-19 and wrote to the Prime Minister himself. In a sickly ironic twist, he ended up a patient due to lack of PPE and passed away from the disease. His legacy will not be forgotten as his message gains urgency and his family and local community mourn the loving and selfless doctor. He passed away on 8.4.2020.

Abdul Gellaledin came from Sudan to the UK 30 years ago, and worked transporting elderly patients to and from Kingston hospital in London. He was working as ambulance health care assistant before he died of Covid-19 on 9.4.2020.

Rahima Bibi Sidhane was a midwife and nurse after she moved to the UK from Trinidad in the late 1960s. She was working in Sutton, south London at the Grennell Lodge nursing home, for 20 years and refused to retire when she died of Covid19 on 20.4.2020 (she was 68).

Dr Muhanad Nowar Eltayib was a cardiac surgeon working at Royal Victoria Hospital in Belfast and was of Sudanese descent, having studied medicine in Sudan. He had been self-isolating with coronavirus symptoms and was found dead in his apartment. Colleagues at the hospital in which he worked called him a beautiful human being and he will be sorely missed. He passed away on the 20th of April.

Dr Sadeq Elhowsh was an orthopaedic surgeon who worked for St Helens and Knowsley Teaching Hospital in Merseyside and was of Libyan descent. He had been working at St Helens for more than 17 years and was a much loved colleague to all who knew him. He will be sorely missed. He passed away on the 20th of April.

Dr Yusuf Patel was a GP who worked in Woodgrange Medical Practice East London and was well known for providing assistance and care within the local community and beyond. He was held in high esteem by his colleagues and patients who spoke of their sadness on his passing. He passed away on the 20th of April.

Dr Yunes Ramadan Teinaz, a public health doctor of Libyan descent and was working in London passed away on the 21st of April. He will be sorely missed.

Dr Medhat Atalla was a consultant geriatrician at Doncaster Royal Infirmary. He was born in Egypt and studied there before coming to the UK in the early 2000s. He was cherished by his patients and colleagues who described him as gentle and caring. He will be greatly missed. He passed away on the 22nd of April.

Dr Nasir Khan was a consultant in acute medicine in Bolton hospital. He was 48 years of age and originated from Pakistan. He will be sorely missed by his family, friends and colleagues. He contracted Covid-19 and was admitted to the ICU before he passed away on 28.4.2020.